

Assessing the Financial Viability of a 1 MW Floating Solar Mini-Grid for Last-Mile Electrification: A Case Study of Islands on Lake Volta

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Keywords

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Executive Summary

This report assesses the financial viability of a proposed 1 MW floating solar photovoltaic (PV) mini-grid system designed to supply electricity to island communities on Lake Volta near Kete Krachi in Ghana's Oti Region. These communities remain unconnected to the national grid due to their geographical isolation and rely on costly and unreliable energy sources. Using the FINPLAN financial modelling tool, the study evaluates project viability under baseline assumptions and key uncertainties through sensitivity analysis.

The results show that the project is financially viable under the base case, with a positive Net Present Value (NPV) of GHS5.59 million and an acceptable Internal Rate of Return (IRR) of 12.415. However, the analysis reveals strong sensitivity to Peak Sun Hours (PSH), electricity tariff levels, and capital expenditure (CAPEX). The project becomes financially unviable when PSH declines to approximately 4.7 hours, when CAPEX overruns exceed 21%, or when tariffs fall below 1.6 GHS/kWh.

The findings highlight the need for supportive policy frameworks, cost-control measures, and tariff-setting mechanisms that balance financial sustainability with social affordability in last-mile electrification projects.

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1 Introduction

Ghana has made significant progress in expanding electricity access, achieving a national electrification rate of approximately 89.5%, one of the highest in Sub-Saharan Africa (Commission, 2024). Despite this achievement, persistent disparities remain, particularly in remote, island, and hard-to-reach communities where extending the national grid is technically challenging and economically prohibitive (Asuamah, Gyamfi and Dagoumas, 2021). These “last-mile” populations continue to face limited or unreliable access to modern energy services, constraining local economic development and social outcomes.

Recognising the central role of energy in national development, the Government of Ghana has prioritised universal electricity access through policies such as the National Energy Policy and the Renewable Energy Act, alongside flagship programs including the National Electrification Scheme (NES) and the Self-Help Electrification Programme (SHEP) (MoE, 2010; Government of Ghana, 2011). While Ghana’s electricity generation mix has historically been dominated by hydropower and thermal sources, increasing climate variability, particularly prolonged droughts affecting hydropower reservoirs, has underscored the need for diversification and greater system resilience.

In response, Ghana is gradually advancing its energy transition agenda by promoting renewable energy deployment, with solar photovoltaics emerging as a strategic option for decentralised electrification. Decentralised solar mini-grids and standalone systems offer a cost-effective and climate-resilient pathway to bridge the last-mile access gap, especially in island and rural communities where grid extension costs are high (Saulo *et al.*, 2015; Comello *et al.*, 2017). These systems not only enhance energy security but also support productive uses of energy, improve service delivery, and contribute to

broader sustainable development objectives. The economic viability of solar PV mini-grids is fundamentally dependent on solar resource availability. Peak sun hours (PSH), which represent effective solar radiation duration, directly influence PV electricity generation and, by extension, project revenues. Variations in PSH therefore have significant implications for key financial indicators, including Net Present Value (NPV), Internal Rate of Return (IRR), and other economic performance metrics. Recent studies indicate that climate change is increasingly affecting solar PV output, primarily through rising temperatures and increased cloud cover, which reduce system efficiency and overall energy production (Adigun *et al.*, 2025). Similarly, capital expenditure (CapEx) overruns and tariff levels are critical determinants of the financial viability of solar power plants (S. Pillai *et al.*, 2026).

1.1 Purpose and Scope

The study will evaluate the financial performance of a 1MW Floating Solar Plant in island communities on Lake Volta near Kete Krachi in Ghana's Oti Region using factors such as investment costs, operational expenses, revenue generation, projected cash flows, and return on investment. The location of the plant is shown in *Figure 1*

Figure 1: Study Area (source:Authors' work)

1.2 Objectives and Aims

The purpose of this study is to evaluate the financial viability and robustness of a 1 MW solar PV mini-grid system serving island communities near Kete Krachi using the FINPLAN modelling tool.

1.2.1 Specific Objectives

To evaluate the minimum profitability and financial robustness of the power plant through sensitivity analysis by:

1. Assessing the impact of reductions in average annual Peak Sun Hours (PSH)

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2. Examining the project's financial performance under increased capital expenditure (CapEx)
 3. Evaluating the sensitivity of project revenues and profitability to changes in electricity tariff levels

2 Methodology

2.1 Modelling Approach and Tool

The analysis employs FINPLAN, a financial planning and project appraisal tool used for evaluating energy infrastructure investments(Oyinna *et al.*, 2025). FINPLAN enables detailed modelling of project cash flows, financing structures, debt service coverage, dividends, and key financial indicators such as NPV and IRR over the project lifetime.

2.2 Data Sources

The technical, financial, and economic assumptions applied in the FINPLAN model were derived from a combination of site-specific data and secondary sources relevant to the study area. Technical inputs, including system configuration and expected energy output, were informed by field information and project design parameters.

Macroeconomic indicators such as inflation rates, exchange rates, and related financial variables were sourced from the Bank of Ghana to ensure consistency with prevailing national economic conditions. Additional sector-specific data were obtained from peer-reviewed journals, policy documents, and reports covering Ghana's energy sector, as well as international literature on mini-grid development and renewable energy projects in remote and island contexts.

These sources provided benchmarks for capital expenditure (CapEx), operational expenditure (OpEx), tariff assumptions, and performance parameters. Together, they form the basis for the key assumptions used in the financial modelling.

2.3 Key Assumptions

The proposed system has an installed capacity of 1 MW and generates approximately 2 GWh annually. Construction spans three years, with commercial operation beginning in 2029 and an economic life of 25 years. Total investment costs are estimated at USD 2.4 million in debt and GHS 11.2 million in equity. The project is financed through 30% equity and 70% concessional debt at a 6% interest rate over 12 years. Electricity is sold at an initial tariff of 1.8 GHS/kWh, escalating with inflation. Local inflation is assumed at 5%, USD inflation at 2%, and the exchange rate at USD 1 = GHS 10.9. In line with (APRA, 2024) and the (Ministry of Energy, 2021), renewable energy components, including solar panels, are exempt from taxes; consequently, a zero tax rate was applied in the analysis. A discount rate of 10% was adopted for the financial evaluation.

2.4 Sensitivity Analysis

Sensitivity analysis using FINPLAN to assess the robustness of the financial viability of the proposed 1 MW solar mini grid for island electrification under key technical, financial, and market uncertainties. Given the capital-intensive nature of mini-grid projects and the unique risks associated with island and last-mile electrification, selected variables are systematically varied to evaluate their impact on core financial indicators, including Net Present Value (NPV), Internal Rate of Return (IRR), Dividends, and Standby facility. The following is the sensitivity analysis conducted.

2.4.1 Reduction in Peak Sun Hours (PSH) effects on NPV, IRR, Dividends, and Standby facility

Solar energy output is highly sensitive to solar resource availability. Islands may experience higher cloud cover, seasonal variability, or micro-climatic effects that reduce effective solar generation (Adigun *et al.*, 2025). A reduction in PSH lowers annual energy production, directly reducing revenues while fixed costs remain unchanged. Climate change poses a threat to the global solar energy potential by reducing the amount of solar radiation reaching the PV cells by 10–15%, as rising cloud cover and temperature-induced efficiency declines of 0.4%–0.5% per °C, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia. (Adigun *et al.*, 2025).

Study indicates that in the Canary Islands, photovoltaic (PV) electricity production is projected to decline by more than 5% by the end of the 21st century, with similar trends expected for mainland Spain. Across Europe, only marginal changes in the temporal stability of solar energy potential are projected across all seasons. In Africa, a reduction in average annual solar potential is anticipated throughout the 21st century, except in specific regions such as the northern coast and areas around 10°S (Araújo, Santos and Abrahão, 2024). To assess the impacts of climate change and its associated effects on solar resource availability, variations in peak sun hours were introduced to evaluate potential changes in solar exposure. These variations directly affect energy generation and, consequently, the economic viability of the project.

The adjusted peak sun hours were applied to estimate changes in energy output, and the resulting energy production values were then used as inputs into the FINPLAN model, as shown in Table 1

Table 1: Impacts of Peak Sun hours (PSH) on Energy output (GWh)

Peak Sun Hours (PSH)	Energy (GWh) Input
5.5	2.0075
5.3	1.9345
5.1	1.8615
4.9	1.7885
4.7	1.7155
4.5	1.6425
4.3	1.5695
4.1	1.4965
3.9	1.4235
3.7	1.3505

2.4.2 Electricity Tariff Variation

Tariff levels directly determine project revenue and are often constrained by affordability considerations and regulatory limits in rural and island communities. This sensitivity evaluates the minimum tariff required for cost recovery and financial sustainability, as well as the extent to which tariffs can be reduced while maintaining acceptable returns. It also highlights the trade-off between financial viability and social affordability. The FINPLAN model applied a tariff variation of $\pm 5\%$ around the base tariff of GHS 1.80/kWh. This rate is based on the minimum energy consumption tariff gazetted by the Public Utilities Regulatory Commission (PURC) for the first quarter of 2026 (PURC, 2026)

2.4.3 Capital Expenditure (CAPEX) Overruns

Island mini-grid projects face elevated logistics and transportation costs, including boat transport, limited local infrastructure, and higher installation expenses. Cost overruns during procurement and construction can significantly weaken project economics. This sensitivity examines how increases in upfront investment affect project returns and financial sustainability. According to a study, Madagascar's geographical isolation from

the East African mainland poses significant logistical challenges, increasing transportation costs and intensifying the effects of supply-chain disruptions, which in turn lead to project delays and higher capital expenditure (CapEx) (Pailman *et al.*, 2025). Furthermore, delays in port clearance can lead to demurrage charges, thereby increasing capital expenditure (CapEx).

For this study, sensitivity analysis was performed by applying a 3% increase in capital expenditure (CapEx), which was then used as an input parameter in the FINPLAN model.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Base Case Results

Under baseline assumptions, the project demonstrates financial viability, generating a positive NPV of GHS5.59 million and 12.4% internal rate of return. Dividend distribution begins 7 years after commissioning, reflecting the capital-intensive nature of the project and the debt repayment profile.

3.2 Sensitivity 1: Peak Sun Hours (PSH)

A decline in average annual peak sun hours (PSH) has a significant impact on energy generation and project revenues. The results indicate a direct, near-linear relationship between reductions in PSH and decreases in electricity output, underscoring the sensitivity of solar PV performance to solar resource availability as shown in Figure 2 .

Figure 2: Impacts of PSH on Energy Production

Lower energy production subsequently weakens key financial indicators, including Net Present Value (NPV) and Internal Rate of Return (IRR). At approximately 4.7 hours of PSH, the project becomes financially unviable, characterised by a negative NPV and delayed or foregone dividend payments, as shown in Figure 3. Furthermore, each 0.2-hour reduction in PSH is estimated to postpone dividend commencement by approximately 1–2 years, highlighting the project’s vulnerability to climate-induced variability in solar resources. As energy production declines due to reductions in peak sun hours (PSH), the project increasingly relies on borrowed funds to sustain operations, as internally generated revenues become insufficient to cover costs. Consequently, the standby financing requirement rises as PSH decreases. This dynamic also affects stakeholder dividends, eroding expected benefits and extending the payback period, thereby delaying returns on investment, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 3: PSH Variations Impact on NPV and IRR

Figure 4: Impacts of PSH variation on the Stand by facility and project dividend

3.3 Sensitivity 2: Capital Expenditure (CAPEX)

The project remains viable under CAPEX increases of up to approximately 18%. Beyond a 21% cost overrun (around GHS 45 million), NPV turns negative, and IRR falls below acceptable levels, as shown in Figure 5

Figure 5: Change in CapEx on NPV and IRR

Although dividends are still possible under moderate overruns, their timing is significantly delayed, reducing project attractiveness to investors. The "white" areas represent years with zero dividends (delays), while the colour intensity shows the growth of the dividend over time. The payout "staircase" shifts significantly to the right as CAPEX increases. The base case delivers earlier and higher dividends, starting around 2036 and steadily increasing toward 2052. As CapEx rises (+3% to +30%), dividend commencement is progressively delayed, and overall dividend levels decline. Higher CapEx scenarios also exhibit lower peak dividends, reflecting reduced project profitability and longer payback periods as shown in Figure 6

Figure 6: Impact of CapEx increase on stakeholder dividends

3.4 Sensitivity 3: Electricity Tariff Variation

Tariff levels strongly influence revenue and financial sustainability. The minimum tariff required for cost recovery is approximately 1.6 GHS/kWh. A tariff reduction of about 11% from the base case remains feasible, but delays dividend payments. Further reductions render the project financially unviable. Figure 7 illustrates how the tariff levels directly influence project profitability, as reflected in both Net Present Value (NPV) and Internal Rate of Return (IRR). At lower tariffs (around GHS 1.5/kWh), the project records a negative NPV, indicating financial infeasibility despite a modest IRR. As tariffs increase, NPV rises steadily from negative to strongly positive, showing improved cash flows and stronger economic viability. Similarly, IRR increases almost linearly with tariff, moving from single digits to roughly 17–18% at GHS 2.4/kWh, reflecting enhanced investment attractiveness.

Figure 7: Tariff impact on NPV and IRR

4 Discussion

4.1 Insights and Implications

The results confirm that the floating solar mini-grids can be financially viable solutions for island electrification, but their success depends on carefully managing technical and financial risks. Solar resource variability emerges as a critical risk, especially in the context of climate change, which may reduce solar irradiation by 10–15% in tropical regions. This underscores the importance of conservative resource assessments and potential hybridisation with other renewable or storage technologies.

The CapEx sensitivity analysis underscores the structural cost vulnerabilities inherent in island-based energy projects, particularly those arising from elevated logistics and transportation requirements, including lake transport and constrained local infrastructure. These factors amplify exposure to component price volatility and supply-chain disruptions, which can materially alter the financial performance and bankability of mini-grid investments. Variations in equipment costs relative to prevailing market benchmarks have the potential to significantly shift project economics, affecting returns and payback periods. Consistent with findings in the mini-grid and remote electrification literature, streamlining procurement processes, strengthening local supply chains, and minimising bureaucratic delays are critical levers for reducing cost overruns and improving project viability, investor confidence, and long-term financial sustainability.

Tariff sensitivity results reveal a fundamental trade-off between financial viability and social affordability. Policymakers may need to consider targeted subsidies, viability gap funding, or results-based financing mechanisms to ensure affordability without undermining investor confidence or burdening low-income demographics. Support during periods of low solar output could further enhance project resilience. Providing

supplementary financial buffers during periods of low solar yield would further safeguard the project against resource-driven volatility

4.2 Limitations

A key limitation of this study is its reliance on assumed capital costs and projected energy production values used in the FINPLAN model. As a result, the financial outcomes may differ from actual project performance, particularly where site-specific conditions, market price fluctuations, or operational realities vary from the modeled assumptions.

4.3 Future Research

Future research will extend this study by incorporating additional sources of uncertainty such as demand variability, battery replacement cycles, and currency fluctuations, into the FINPLAN framework to improve the robustness of financial projections. The model outputs will also be validated using empirical data from operational mini-grid projects, enabling comparison between simulated and real-world performance. These enhancements will strengthen the analytical depth of the current study and support the development of more context-specific financial assessment tools.

5 Conclusion

This study demonstrates that a 1 MW solar mini-grid for island communities on Lake Volta is financially viable under baseline conditions but highly sensitive to solar resource availability, capital costs, and tariff levels. The project becomes unviable when PSH declines to approximately 4.7 hours, CAPEX overruns exceed 21%, or tariffs fall below 1.6 GHS/kWh.

The findings underscore the importance of robust financial modelling and enabling policy frameworks in enhancing the viability of renewable energy and mini-grid projects. The government should introduce targeted support mechanisms for project developers during periods of reduced energy output, while maintaining an appropriate balance between financial sustainability and the social affordability of electricity tariffs. These efforts should be complemented by streamlined regulatory and administrative processes, including accelerated permitting and approvals, to minimise bureaucratic delays and mitigate the risk of cost overruns. At the same time, maintaining a stable macroeconomic environment, particularly through effective exchange rate and inflation management, is critical to reducing project cost uncertainties and strengthening investor confidence in the renewable energy and mini-grid sector.

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